

Gambarova Ruhiyya Mantiq*Assoc. Prof.***Abbasova Yegana Aziz***Assoc. Prof.**Azerbaijan State Agrarian University, Ganja***ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ НА УСТОЙЧИВОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ И ИХ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ****Гамбарова Рухийя Мантик***Доцент***Аббасова Егяна Азиз***Доцент**Азербайджанский Государственный Аграрный Университет, Гянджа***Abstract**

Sustainable economic development means the implementation of the transfer of resources to future generations through the efficient use of resources and the preservation of balance by taking into account social and environmental issues during economic development. For many years, the failure to take into account social and environmental issues while taking steps related to economic development has led to the emergence of social crises and global environmental problems. The issue of balanced economic development has been reflected in the norms adopted by international and regional organizations, as well as by individual states. In this regard, the importance and relevance of the concept of sustainable economic development should be emphasized in light of the above.

Аннотация

Устойчивое экономическое развитие означает осуществление передачи ресурсов будущим поколениям путем эффективного использования ресурсов и сохранения баланса путем учета социальных и экологических вопросов в процессе экономического развития. На протяжении многих лет игнорирование социальных и экологических вопросов при принятии мер по экономическому развитию приводило к возникновению социальных кризисов и глобальных экологических проблем. Проблема сбалансированного экономического развития нашла отражение в нормах, принятых международными и региональными организациями, а также отдельными государствами. В этой связи следует подчеркнуть важность и актуальность концепции устойчивого экономического развития в свете вышеизложенного.

Keywords: sustainable development, economic development, sustainability, etc.**Ключевые слова:** устойчивое развитие, экономическое развитие, устойчивость и т. д.

In order for states to reach a high level of socio-economic well-being, it is essential for them to develop their national economies. In this regard, the main issue facing states is to ensure the stability of national economic development. Here, stability means the continuous and sustainable development of the national economy, the completion of periods of economic decline with minimal losses due to pre-planned policies, and the achievement of maximum growth during periods of growth. [1]

During the 19th and 20th centuries, the sharp rise in industrialization and the exploitation of natural resources by states led to a deterioration in the ecological situation, which in turn led to a decline in social living standards in countries. At the same time, the worsening of the ecological situation and the gradual deterioration of the world's existing natural resources have increased concerns that the planet's resources will not be properly transferred to future generations. The concept of sustainability is one of the least understood concepts in economic terms. Thus, the concept of sustainability has been approached by different scholars with different theoretical perspectives.

A number of scholars attribute the first traces of the concept of sustainable development to David Ricardo, Thomas Malthus and John Stuart Mill, representatives of the classical political economy school.

Thomas Malthus touched on the limits of growth and increase, emphasized that the limited area and resources, and the continuous increase in population would further increase the scarcity of resources, and therefore defended the idea that growth should be limited. [2]

David Ricardo argued in a similar vein, noting that the amount of land available for use is small compared to the rate of population growth, and that as more and more land is required to meet the needs of a growing population, its productivity will decline due to overexploitation. According to Ricardo, the decline in land productivity will in turn be accompanied by a decline in natural growth.[3]

According to John Stuart Mill, the growth of well-being among people can only increase as a result of mutual understanding and ensuring sustainability. The mentioned thoughts of the scientists who are representatives of the classical school actually constitute the theoretical foundation of the concept of sustainable development, which was conceptualized on theoretical grounds in the 20th century. However, the thoughts of the classical economists about the self-renewal of natural resources and their large potential reserves have long led to the reduction of attention to environmental issues by their successors, economists, which has led to the exploitation of natural resources. According to

these thoughts, the reserves of natural resources are infinite and the process of obtaining products from them in the production process is also infinite. What is important is to convert these resources into finished products that meet the needs of people, and it is not important to pay attention to the external effects that will arise at this stage.

Along with the theoretical foundation of the representatives of the classical political economy school, the first practical traces of the concept of sustainable development can be found in the policies related to forest management developed in Europe in the 17th and 18th centuries. [4]

In the 17th century, the rapid depletion of wood resources in England led to the idea, advocated by John Evelyn in 1662, that the massive exploitation of trees had disrupted the ecological balance. According to him, it was a national duty to protect trees, prevent their massive exploitation, and continuously plant new trees to maintain the balance. This approach of John Evelyn was reflected in the *Sylva* document prepared by him. In this respect, the *Sylva* document can be considered one of the first documents in which the concept of sustainable development was defended and its importance was emphasized. [5]

In 1713, John Evelyn and the French minister Jean Batis Colbert developed the concept of sustainable forest management, based on the ideas of Hans von Karlowitz. Influenced by his research, forestry was formulated as a science by Alexander von Humboldt and Georg Ludwig Hartig. All these early studies influenced Aldo Leopold's formulation of the ethics of land use in the 1960s.

Theoretical views on sustainable development are also included in the works written by A. Pigou. There are traces of the concept of sustainable development in his books on economics written in 1912 and 1920. According to A. Pigou, three capitals are needed for a person to achieve prosperity:

1. natural resources
2. substances produced by man
3. human resources and intellectual resources

According to A. Pigou, the three resources mentioned complement each other and the weakening of one can be restored or compensated by effectively using the other two. However, this theoretical approach is currently approached differently and the idea that natural resources can be compensated for in the event of their weakening and being relegated to the background is not accepted. The theoretical approaches of A. Pigou and those who believe that natural resources are less important are expressed in modern scientific literature with the concept of "weak sustainability". [6]

After the Second World War, the concept of ecological balance and sustainability entered a new stage in the world. Long-lasting destructive wars had severely damaged the economies of developed countries as well as the ecosystem. The approach to the economy and development of Keynesianism, which was the dominant economic thought after the Second World War, did not take sustainable development into account. Thus, in order to restore the destroyed economies, states mainly spent all their efforts on developing

their economies at any cost and at the same time exploiting nature. At this time, in order to achieve economic development and growth, the issues of environmental imbalance and the lack of sustainable development at the local level were accepted. In this way, massive exploitation of raw materials was carried out. Although the states were eventually able to restore their economies, this was at the expense of further aggravating the existing environmental situation.

In 1962, the book "Silent Spring" written by Rachel Carson played an important role in the emergence of new theoretical views on sustainable development. This book touched on the relationship between environmental protection movements, economic development and growth, and the disruption of the ecological balance. The book especially touched on theoretical development issues related to agriculture and emphasized that if sustainable development policies were not applied in this area, natural resources would not be preserved and passed on to future generations. Although Rachel Carson's book "Silent Spring" was met with dissatisfaction because it drew attention to the serious impact of agricultural chemicals on the soil, it led to developments in approaches to the environment and sustainable development due to its successes. The resistance of states to the concept of sustainable development changed in a different direction only in the 1970s. Thus, it became clear that during these times, local ecological balance problems that had arisen as a result of intensive exploitation, which had been ignored since World War II, had developed and moved to the regional and even global level. The first approaches that were close to the currently accepted definition of the concept of sustainable development were taken from the 1972 report on the Limits to Growth of the Club of Rome by Dennis Meadows and Donella Meadows, employees of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. The authors defined the concept they adopted to protect the global ecological balance as "a model of development of the world that is sustainable without sudden and disorderly collapse and can meet the necessary needs of all people." The report touched on the issues of massive exploitation of resources and environmental pollution threatening the sustainability of life, and emphasized the balance between economic development and the ecosystem [7]

One of the steps that played an important role in the development of the concept of sustainable development was the UN Conference on the Human Environment, organized by the UN in Stockholm in June 1972. The preparations for this conference took 4 years, and more than thirty million dollars were spent on the implementation and organization of the conference, which was attended by 115 countries. At this conference, the environment in which man is surrounded, the resources he exploits, the ecosystem that is being destroyed as a result, the intensifying global ecological problems were brought to the agenda, and the issues of protecting resources in a way that future generations can use them effectively were discussed.

The following declarations were adopted at the aforementioned conference regarding the provision of sustainable development:

1. Human rights must be protected, discrimination and colonialism must be condemned.
2. Natural resources must be protected.
3. The potential for using alternative energy sources of the world must be protected.
4. Living things in nature must be protected.
5. Exhaustible resources must be distributed efficiently and must not be depleted.
6. Environmental pollution should not exceed the self-recovery limit of nature.
7. Pollution of the oceans to the extent that it will be harmful to them should be prevented.
8. Economic development is necessary to prevent environmental pollution.
9. Developing countries should be helped to develop their economies.

One of the steps that further strengthens the concept of sustainable development in the world is the introduction of the concept of "ecological development". Ecological development is understood as the economic development that effectively uses the economic potential and resources of the environment we live in at the regional and local levels, taking into account the environment and other environmental issues. The concepts of "sustainable development of the world system in a balanced manner" and "ecological development" put forward by Dennis Meadows and Donella Meadows were first accepted as official concepts in the "Our Common Future" report of the UN Commission on Environment and Development. Thus, the concept of sustainable development began to be accepted and used by international organizations related to political and social life in the world. After the "Our Common Future" report, this issue was again brought to the agenda in the "Caring for the Earth: A Strategy for Sustainable Living" report. In the aforementioned report, the theoretical principles of the concept of sustainable development were developed and adapted to strategies that can be applied in practice. Another factor that makes this report important is that it also covers the issue of sustainable development of the economy. Here, not only the problems of using vital resources, but also the prob-

lems of quality of life are touched upon. In the 21st century, attention to the concept of sustainable development has increased even more. Thus, in the 20th century and earlier, the meetings and thoughts expressed on sustainable development were more of a theoretical basis and a determination of approaches. Currently, countries around the world are trying to implement the issue of ensuring sustainable development by jointly cooperating in such works as solving global climate problems in the world, preventing desertification, atmospheric problems, and preventing large-scale wars that could destroy the ecosystem. In addition to global environmental issues, cooperation at the level of regional and global organizations has increased and the work has been carried out to a practical level in issues such as working on the development of human capital in order to achieve effective economic development, supporting the effective development of human resources in developing countries, increasing attention to children's education, preventing the exploitation of women and children's labor, supporting the development of the health system in underdeveloped countries, and implementing industrialization in accordance with the principles of sustainable development.

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